

APPLICATION OF GEOGRAPHIC INFORMATION SYSTEMS ON LAND ADMINISTRATION AND MANAGEMENT IN NIGERIA: USERS EXPERIENCE

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Abstract

Conventional land administration techniques rely on manual record keeping, leading to design and implementation projects that require excessively prolonged durations. Technological improvements have resulted in more efficient, intricate, and accelerated execution of tasks associated with land administration. These improvements include the use of the Geographic Information System (GIS). Efficient urban land management depends on the availability of high-quality, reliable, and prompt information. Geographic Information Systems (GIS) technology can validate this information by digitising land records. The conventional method of managing land records in the majority of land registries nationwide is no longer viable in the modern information era due to its intrinsic difficulties. This study employs a quantitative research design, utilising a purposive sampling method to engage the ABIA (GIS) staff. Out of the 97 questionnaires distributed to ABIAGIS staff, 72 were returned and found useful for this exercise. The findings reveal that 33% claimed there was no improvement in land administration and management, 22% claimed that the introduction of GIS made their work easier and seamless, and only 20% were highly competent in the use of GIS software. This implied that a lot of investment needs to be carried out, especially in the area of training, funding, research and development amongst the users. This will bring about a humongous benefit in the area of land administration and management in Abia State, Nigeria.

Keywords: Estate Surveyors, Geographic Information System, Land Administration.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

In the view of Sundaram, Sowjanya, Andavar, and Reddy (2018), as well as Akeh and Mshelia (2016), argue that land is critical to human development and survival. Land is a vital resource for humanity, acting as the cornerstone for all development operations (Akeh and Mshelia, 2016). Land is an important component of national wealth in several countries, therefore its management is critical for human survival and growth (Akeh and Mshelia, 2016). Land administration, which is part of the larger framework of land management, is defined in the United Nations Land Administration Guidelines (United Nations Economic Commission for Europe, 1996) as the process of gathering, documenting, and disseminating information about land ownership, valuation, and use in the implementation of land management policies.

According to Dale (2020), land administration includes identifying land rights and other features, surveying and delineating such lands, detailed recording, and disseminating relevant information about the land and any linked properties. In Nigeria, the Ministry of Lands, Survey, and Town Planning is in charge of managing land and resources for the long-term use and benefit of all populations (Magaji and Umar, 2020). The importance of land for ecological health and existence necessitates this commitment, since any absence of management may

result in disorder, including disputes and conflicts (Asaaga, 2021). Given the developmental challenges that typically result from such turmoil, it is critical that land administration duties, such as title issuance, security management, land registry oversight, land policy consultancy, general conveyance, development control, and physical planning, be carried out effectively and efficiently. From a Nigerian perspective, reports of inefficiency appear to have followed the ministries' fulfilment of these commitments. The system is fraught with challenges, including inadequate customer responsiveness due to order processing delays for Certificates of Occupancy (C of O), rigid land policies, modifications of layout plans and deed documents, deficient record-keeping, outdated cadastral mapping systems, mismanagement of land expropriation, lack of standardisation, ineffective stakeholder engagement, among others (Abolade et al., 2018; Adeniyi et al., 2018; Madumere, 2019; Obi-Aso, 2020; Scholars and practitioners have investigated the significance and effectiveness of information and communications technology (ICT) systems, including Geographic Information Systems (GIS) (Abolade et al., 2018; Akey and Mshelia, 2016; Atazadeh et al., 2017; Kalogianni et al., 2020; Moreri et al., 2018; Nissi et al., 2021). This is especially relevant in African countries where digitalisation is not widely adopted due to a lack of policy consistency and capacity (Badaru and Mphahlele, 2023). These difficulties have been recognised as factors influencing the quality of land administration and management. An examination of the literature reveals a lack of empirical research into the users experience of GIS on land administration and management in Nigeria. This demonstrates a dearth of empirical evidence on the usefulness and efficiency of GIS in Nigeria. To address the highlighted knowledge gap, this study investigates the users experience of GIS on land administration and management in Abia State, Nigeria.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

Notwithstanding technology developments and the accessibility of GIS, the land challenge remains significant. Angel et al. (2011) predict that by 2030, the urban population in developing nations would attain 4 billion. Numerous cities lack effective policies for expansion, hindering the creation of enough open spaces, efficient transportation systems, and sustainable population densities (Barry, 2014). Currently, around 1.1 billion to 4 billion people inhabit slums worldwide (Global Land Tools Network, 2011). The employment of most individuals is unstable. Failure to address this issue may result in societal and political instability (GLTN, 2011). Barry (2014) contends that following World War II, a multitude of substantial land titling and registration programs (1.1 billion) have been implemented in developing countries, based on the assumption that titles bolster land tenure security and stimulate economic activity by improving access to finance.

The research substantially corroborated this notion. The scale of the study is a crucial element. The study performed by Dey de Soto (2000). Nevertheless, many titling programs have demonstrated ineffectiveness (Global Report, 2007; study report on human settlements). This study presents numerous enquiries: what are the strategic alternatives? Approximately 30% of land in developing nations is formally documented or recorded (Zevenbergen, Augustinus, Antonio, 2012). In numerous African countries, the percentage is significantly lower; in Nigeria, for example, it nears 3% (Barry, 2006). The author asserts that 370 million indigenous

peoples occupy 90 countries, live in some of the most biologically diverse places, which are threatened as their traditional claims often rely on oral tradition rather than documented proof (Barry, 2006). They constitute 5% of the global population, 15% of the world's destitute, and nearly one-third of the 900 million individuals classified as extremely poor (Barry, 2006). The creation of legislative structures and documents to enhance tenure security for this population is inadequate.

This challenge presents several strategies for achieving tenure security, especially within the framework of globalisation that necessitates individuals to conform to a neoliberal modernisation paradigm. Forcing individuals to comply with these rules is being characterised as the new colonialism. These cultures are not vestiges of a bygone era. They are continually evolving, and their governance and economic frameworks may exhibit configurations significantly different from those of developed nations. Many conflicts inside nations, across regions, and among communities are articulated and intensified about borders and access to natural resources, such as minerals, timber, water, and grazing area. The primary causes may be more strongly linked to political exclusion, social prejudice, and economic marginalisation (Barry, 2014). Land functions as a source of sustenance, identity, history, and culture, making it prone to become a centre of conflict (United Nations Interagency Framework Team for Preventative Action, 2012). Corruption is quite pervasive in the land sector (United Nations, 2013).

Numerous entities administer area within a defined jurisdiction. Enhancing management and organisational development strategies is a more effective solution to facilitate their cooperation and information sharing than extensive organisational restructuring or the adoption of a new registration system. Inherent tensions arise between economic growth strategies that exploit land and the principles of justice and equity in human rights, endangering the livelihoods of vulnerable communities, including the underprivileged, minorities, and those marginalised within traditional cultures. These tribes often face displacement due to commercial activities such as agriculture and mining. In familial circumstances, women, the elderly, and children are more susceptible to eviction during divorce or separation. While real property law and related tools can protect fundamental rights, they may also perpetuate injustice, resulting in the loss of long-held land ownership (Barry, 2014).

As a result, the issue of governance and land governance should be a priority for any nation. The notions of governance, land governance, and transparency have been progressively significant in development discourse. The differentiation between "governance" and "good government" has emerged in recent times. The Washington Consensus on development asserted that successful governance should enhance market efficiency and promote institutional reform (Sundaram and Chowdhury, 2012). The economic impetus for interest in governance in emerging nations stems from the substantial increase in investment in these countries and the associated risks to investors' assets (Arndt and Oman, 2006). The World Bank Worldwide Governance Indicators (WGI), established in 1996, comprise six indicators derived from over 300 sub-indicators and factors (Sundaram and Chowdhury, 2012). The latest edition includes: i voice and accountability; ii political stability and absence of violence; iii government

effectiveness; iv regulatory quality; v rule of law; and vi control of corruption. The developers of the indicators assert that substantial empirical evidence substantiates a causal relationship between enhanced governance and superior development results (Sundaram and Chowdhury, 2012; Kaufmann, Kraay, and Zoido, 1999).

The assessments are derived on evaluations of governance quality in various nations. This include expert surveys, country assessments by risk evaluation entities, and cross-national population surveys done by international organisations and NGOs (Kaufmann et al., 1999). This worldwide initiative impacts investment choices concerning particular nations and the anticipations of contributors regarding development initiatives. As a result, the indicators, their utilisation, and the technique for their formulation have been rigorously evaluated. A multitude of analysts offer significant critiques of the indicators. The validity of the indicators, procedures for calculating related scores, measuring techniques, interpretative frameworks, and applications is scrutinised.

Many critics contend that assessing perceptions of governance is imprecise. The system exhibits over sensitivity, hindering sound growth decisions. Changes in the indicators and metrics employed for measurement have led to significant differences in the results. In the preliminary stage of the initiative, metrics were employed to promote a neoliberal development ideology, which posits that limited government results in superior governance, and that conventional governance institutions, such as customary leadership in developing nations, are inferior to contemporary models. The theory asserts that efficient governance and an optimised government promote economic development (Sundaram and Chowdhury, 2012). Empirical evidence suggests that economic development may enhance governance rather than serve as a prelude to it (Barry, 2014).

Recent instances encompass China, Vietnam, and Cambodia. Numerous industrialised nations failed to attain effective governance or economic advancement through this essential methodology. Economic development can be more successfully achieved through strategies that persist despite governmental deficiencies (Sundaram and Chowdhury, 2012). Certain industrialised economies, marked by minimal governmental interference, demonstrate deficient land administration systems (Barry, 2014). Enhanced governance will facilitate the advancement of human rights and establish a more stable foundation for economic endeavours. Facilitating governance as a driver of economic development might be likened to the advocacy of land title schemes, which were founded on simplistic economic reasoning.

Arguably, this leads to land tenure administration and management using GIS. Geographic Information Systems (GIS) are sophisticated, automated instruments that enable the gathering, analysis, visualisation, simulation, and application of geographical data to enhance decision-making (Franch-Pardo et al., 2021; Wang, 2020). This technique makes spatial data available and usable for decision-making. This is accomplished through the amalgamation of many databases, including geomeia, remote sensing, satellite and aerial photography, and spreadsheets, among others. This is designed for mapping, communication, planning, and reducing environmental impacts (Hussain et al., 2020; Jha and Tukkaraja, 2020; Satria and Castro, 2016). The aim of these integrations is to optimise operations and minimise faults. GIS

technology applications in land administration and management generally target system inefficiencies, notably with forgeries or duplicity, delays in processing client requests, and land use monitoring. Joos (2022) contends that GIS utilises applications such as Esri's proprietary ArcGIS token-based authentication system to regulate data access, specifically in relation to the mitigation of duplicity and forgery. Data access is limited to authorised personnel, and any occurrences of falsification will incur consequences for the accountable party. To accelerate the processing of customer requests, GIS technology utilises geomedias such as Hexagon, allowing consumers to swiftly access vital information, unlike the more time-consuming approach of manually retrieving files and papers (Kahn et al., 2015). The incorporation of these methods contextualises the Nigerian experience within wider global discussions on GIS preparedness for land tenure administration and management.

3.0 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study utilised a quantitative approach to evaluate user experiences with GIS in land administration and management in Abia State, Nigeria. This study utilised a purposive sampling method to collect the perspectives of the respondents. A list of variables identified in the literature was utilised to develop a questionnaire aimed at fulfilling the research objective. The questionnaire was utilised to gather data from ABIAGIS staff regarding land administration and management in Nigeria. The questionnaire consists of two sections: the first section collects demographic information from respondents, and the second section analyses the experience of GIS in land administration within Abia State. This methodology was chosen because it enables researchers to identify individuals who have knowledge of the subject being studied (Creswell and Poth, 2018). The main drawback of purposive sampling is its tendency to introduce bias, as participants are selected based on predetermined criteria, resulting in a non-representative sample that limits the generalisability of the findings to the broader population (Ahmed, 2024). This study mitigated response bias by ensuring the anonymity and confidentiality of responses, employing neutral and explicit survey questions, and utilising diverse data collection methods to validate participant feedback and reduce the influence of social desirability or other biases (Bergen and Labonte, 2019).

4.0 FINDINGS

The author used smart survey questionnaires to elicit responses from the respondents. A total of 97 questionnaires were distributed among ABIAGIS staff through WhatsApp, emails, and Facebook Messenger. A total of 72 were received, and they were found useful for this analysis. Table 1 presented background data on the 72 survey respondents, including age, academic qualification, and work experience. The majority of respondents involved in the survey are above 30 years old, representing 90% of the total respondents, as shown in Table 1. This result shows that the survey respondents are mature enough to be involved in the research. For the academic qualification of the respondents, 71% of the study population have a bachelor's degree and above. For work experience, 73% of the respondents have more than ten years of work experience in practice, and this confirmed respondents' eligibility to be involved in the research.

Table 1: Demographic information on respondents

<i>Respondent's background information</i>	Frequency	Percentage
<i>Age bracket</i>		
21–30 years	7	10
31–40 years	21	29
41–50 years	38	53
51 years and above	6	8
Total	72	100
<i>Highest academic qualification attained</i>		
Ordinary National Diploma	5	7
Higher National Diploma	16	22
Bachelor degree	39	54
Postgraduate Diploma	6	8
Master's degree	5	7
Doctorate degree	1	2
Total	72	100
<i>Work experience</i>		
1–5 Years	2	3
6–10 Years	17	24
11–15 Years	29	40
16–20 Years	19	26
21 and Above	5	7
Total	72	100.00

Source: Author (2025)

4.1 presentation of findings

This section presents the ABIAGIS staff's analysis of the users' experience of GIS in land administration in Abia State, Nigeria, with the question, 'Has there been any improvement in land registration since the introduction of ABIAGIS?' Table 2 below shows the distribution of population responses using a Likert scale of 5, where 1. No improvement 2. Less improvement 3. Improvement 4. Great improvement 5. Excellent improvement.

Table 2: Analysis of the users' experience of GIS in improving land administration in Abia State, Nigeria

S/N	Users experience	Level of Agreement (mean %)				
		1	2	3	4	5
USEX 1	Has there been any improvement in land registration since the introduction of ABIAGIS	33.33%	11.11%	11.11%	22.22%	22.22%

Source: Author: (2025)

From the table above, it indicates that 33.33% claimed that there was no improvement based on their experiences, while 11.11% believed that less improvement was recorded, 11.11% alluded to there being an improvement, and 22.22% believe that they have great and excellent improvement, respectively. The introduction of this new technology should make the workers do their work easier and seamlessly; therefore, the staff were asked if the introduction of

ABIAGIS had made their work easier, which is represented below. Table 3 shows the distribution of population responses using a Likert scale of 5, where 1 is much easier and seamless. 2. Easier 3. Less difficult 4. Difficult 5. More difficult

Table 3: Analysis of the users' experience of GIS in land administration in Abia State, Nigeria

S/N	Users experience	Level of Agreement (mean %)				
		1	2	3	4	5
USEX 2	Has the introduction of ABIAGIS made your work easier and seamless?	22.22%	37.33%	16.17%	17.11%	7.17%

Source: Author (2025)

Table 3 indicates that 22.22% of respondents claimed that GIS technology made their work easier, while 37.33% found it seamless, 16.17% suggested it was less difficult, 17.11% considered it difficult, and 7.17% thought it was more difficult. To unravel how competent the staff were in handling GIS software. The question posed to them was, "If you use GIS software for your work, how competent are you in the use of it?" Table 4 shows the distribution of population responses using a Likert scale of 5, where 1. Highly competent 2. Competent 3. Good 4. Fair 5. No competence

Table 4: Analysis of competency in the users' experience of GIS in land administration in Abia State, Nigeria

S/N	Users experience	Level of Agreement (mean %)				
		1	2	3	4	5
USEX 3	If you use GIS software for your work, how competent are you in the use of them?	20.00%	27.33%	21.92%	21.00%	9.75%

Source: Author (2025)

Table 4 indicates that 20.00% of respondents were highly competent in the use of GIS technology, 27.33% were competent, 21.92% were good, 21.00% were fair, and 9.75% have no competence. To understand the "problems associated with the intended objectives of ABIAGIS," questions were posed to them and analysed by asking ABIAGIS staff if there were any activities working against the good purpose of the establishment of the program. Table 5 shows the distribution of population responses using a Likert scale of 2, where 1. Yes and 2. No.

Table 5: Analysis of the problem associated with the intended objectives of ABIAGIS

S/N	Users experience	Level of Agreement (mean %)	
		Yes	No
USEX 4	Are there any activities working against the good purpose of the establishment of ABIAGIS?	77.78%	22.22%

Source: Author (2025)

Table 5 indicates that 77.78% of respondents claimed there is a problem, whereas 22.22% accentuate that there was no problem associated with the intended objectives of ABIAGIS. The author wanted to know how often the problem occurs. The question posed to them was, “If there are, how do they occur?”

Table 6 shows the distribution of population responses using a Likert scale of 5, where 1. Always 2. Often 3. Sometimes 4. Rarely 5. Never

Table 6: Analysis of how often problems associated with the intended objectives of ABIAGIS occur

S/N	Users experience	Level of Agreement (mean %)				
		1	2	3	4	5
USEX 5	If there are, how do they occur?	32.00%	24.13%	24.92%	11.00%	7.95%

Source: Author (2025)

Table 6 indicates that 32.00% of respondents claimed that the problem always occurs, whereas 24.13% assert that it occurs often, while 24.92% posit that it occurs sometimes, 11.00% stipulate rarely, and 7.95% say never.

In suggesting possible solutions to identified problems in the implementation of ABIAGIS, the respondents were asked to identify possible solutions to the identified problems. Table 7 displays the distribution of population responses based on a 5-point Likert scale, which includes the following options: 1. Availability of GIS software, 2. Retraining of staff, 3. Funding, 4. Digitising land documents, and 5. All of the above.

Table 7: Analysis of possible solutions to identified problems in the implementation of ABIAGIS

S/N	Users experience	Level of Agreement (mean %)				
		1	2	3	4	5
USEX 6	What are the possible solutions to the identified problems?	9.01%	11.09%	18.18%	23.27%	38.45%

Source: Author (2025)

Table 7 indicates that 9.01% of respondents assert the availability of GIS software, 11.09% believed for retraining of the staff, 18.18% believed for funding, 23.27% concurred with digitising land documents, and 38.45% alluded to all of the above.

5.0 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

From the findings above, it can be deduced that only 44% alluded to ABIAGIS as having improved land registration (see Table 2); this can be interpreted as a gap in the GIS project itself. This finding aligns significantly with the work of Dey de Soto (2000) and the Global Report (2007), that many titling programmes have demonstrated ineffectiveness. The reason for this is beyond the scope of this study. However, the author suggests more research to unravel the reasons behind it. Also, table 3 confirms that only 22.22% of the respondents claimed that GIS technology made their work easier; this is worrisome. For example, this implied that GIS

is not living up to expectations in Abia State, Nigeria, as against the belief. Arguably, many factors can be responsible. In the area of competence, only 47% are competent to use the ABIAGIS (see table 4). This raises concern in the quest for the land titling programme in Abia State. In the view of the author, at least, a greater percentage of the respondents should be competent. In terms of any activities working against the good purpose of the establishment of ABIAGIS, the majority of the respondents (77%) conform to the status quo. This also corroborates with the study of the United Nations Inter-Agency Framework Team for Preventative Action (2012) and the United Nations (2013), that land encapsulates essential elements of sustenance, identity, history, and culture, making it susceptible to conflicts and promoting corruption. Very importantly, this study affirmed that this incidence occurred regularly with a representation of 80%; see table 6. This is alarming because nothing meaningful can be achieved in an atmosphere of rancour and disorder. In ameliorating the problem of the underperforming nature of ABIAGIS, the respondents alluded to many factors, such as the availability of GIS software, retraining of staff, funding, and digitising land documents. As Sundaram and Chowdhury (2012) state, these tally round the concepts of governance, land governance, and transparency.

6.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Conversely, the ABIAGIS workers identified several issues and challenges that hinder the achievement of ABIAGIS's set objectives. This report reveals that not all the workers in ABIAGIS can use the GIS software, which is the key to the current management and processing of land administration matters. Those who cannot use GIS software impede the fast-tracking of work, slowing their progress, especially with more clients. A greater percentage of the staff are not competent. This issue may contribute to undermining the positive goals of establishing ABIAGIS. The research identified problems related to fully realising the potential of ABIAGIS staff and pointed out that retraining is essential, particularly because a significant percentage of the staff are not competent in using GIS software. Therefore, for effective deliverables, the staff should be trained and retrained in GIS and its application for efficiency and effectiveness. Again, the workers listed funding as another solution that was needed to tackle some of the problems militating against the achievement of ABIAGIS's set objectives.

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